

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

Guidelines for the geophysical characterization of rockfall protection embankments

SPOKE 4 – DIGITAL INNOVATION TOWARD SUSTAINABLE MOUNTAIN

DELIVERABLE DN.1_RM3 - SUMMER

Version history

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

A) Motivation

Reinforced earth embankments are widely adopted mitigation measures against rockfalls involving multiple events of block impacts with high kinetic energy. A detailed geophysical characterization of these embankments can supply valuable information about their internal structure and mechanical properties. The geophysical prospections can also be used to investigate the lateral homogeneity of the structures and to highlight weaknesses or heterogeneities in the compaction of the constructive materials. The geophysical results can be further used as quantitative input for the numerical modeling of the structural response of the embankments. These results help in reducing the simplifications that are generally affecting the models and in obtaining a more effective characterization of the targets.

B) Proposed workflow

The selected approach for the geophysical characterization of reinforced earth embankments is the results of several tests carried out on real case studies. The proposed workflow is summarized in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Workflow for the geophysical characterization of rockfall protection embankments.

In detail, active and passive seismic methods coupled with electrical resistivity tomography demonstrate to be effective for a deep and comprehensive characterization of the embankment materials. Active seismic methods represent an optimal technique for the estimation of the dynamic elastic moduli and Poisson ratio of the materials. Passive seismic methods can be used to quantify the resonance frequency/ies of the structure. The electrical resistivity tomography can be used to highlight changes in the porosity or degree of saturation along and inside the embankment. All these results represent valuable input for the numerical modeling of the embankment structural response. They can also be used as a proxy to cross-validate the results of the numerical simulations.

C) Acquisition layout and instrumentation

Active seismics

Active seismic inspections generally involve the deployment of a line of geophones at regular spacing. The sensors are connected to the seismograph (digitalization and recording unit) through multichannel cables that run along the line. A seismic source is then positioned at several locations along the line and the shots from each location are acquired at each geophone along the line.

For the characterization of rockfall embankments, the active seismic line deployment and acquisition parameters should satisfy the requirements for seismic reflection and surface wave tomography analyses.

The maximum available space is generally found at the top of the embankment, in longitudinal direction. The seismic line should therefore be deployed in this position, as close as possible to central axis of the embankment. The length of the line should be adequate to investigate to whole thickness of the embankment. As a rule of thumb, it is suggested to deploy a seismic line with a length equal to at least 4-5 times the total height of the embankment. The spacing between the geophones should be comparable to the desired final resolution of the results (max 1-2 m). Depending on the available space and the desired spacing between the different geophones, the required number of sensors can be selected.

As a general suggestion, the recommended test equipment should contemplate the following components:

- 48-channel (min) seismograph, with the possibility of stacking traces related to different shots carried out at the same source location;
- 48 (min) vertical geophones with central frequency equal (or close) to 4.5 Hz;
- seismic source appropriate to the length of the spread; e.g., sledgehammer impacting vertically on a metallic plate;
- synchronization and trigger system.

For tomographic purposes, it is recommended to acquire shots with the source located every 6-8 geophones (max). The acquisition parameters must allow the proper recording of first arrival times at all the geophones (for seismic reflection) and the whole wave train of surface wave (for surface wave analysis or tomography). As a consequence, the total duration of the acquisition (T) must generally be equal to or greater than 0.5 s. The sampling rate should be at least 6 times higher than the highest frequency to be recorded to ensure an adequate sampling interval (dt) for the traces and accurate first arrival time picking.

For each source point, the energization should be repeated a minimum of 5 times in order to perform automatic stacking and improve the signal-to-noise ratio in the saved traces. It is also advisable to use a trigger delay in the recordings of about -0.1 s.

The line edges should be surveyed with appropriate topographic instrumentation (e.g., GPS) so that the line can be properly georeferenced and possible local targets (e.g., weakness zones) might be further located inside the embankment.

Passive seismics

Passive seismic methods use listening capabilities only. As a consequence, no seismic source is needed for the data acquisition. A three-component (3C) high-sensitivity geophone or seismometer is deployed on the top of the

embankment, along the central axis of the structure. The instrument records the ambient seismic noise vibrations that are naturally present or anthropically induced at the site for a long time window. From the analysis of the spectral content of the noise, it is possible to quantify the resonance phenomena occurring inside the embankment.

The instrumentation required for the test is simply including:

- A high-sensitivity 3C low-frequency (<2 Hz) geophone or broadband seismometer;
- A digitizer and recording unit.

The deployment of the 3C sensors need proper orientation of the three components. It is advisable to align the N component of the sensor to the N direction or, better, to the elongation of the embankment.

The measurement can be repeated at several points along the embankment or several stations can be deployed along it, avoiding measurements at the edges of the structures to limit 3D effects.

The total time of the recordings (ambient seismic noise on the three components) at each point should be equal to or greater than 30 minutes to increase the robustness of the results. The suggested sampling frequency is 200-250 Hz

Electrical Resistivity Tomography

Electrical resistivity tomography (ERT) involves the deployment of a line of steel electrodes at regular spacing. The electrodes should be planted in the ground to ensure current injection and flow in the embankment materials. The electrodes are then connected to recording instrument through multichannel cables.

The layout geometry suggested for the electrical resistivity tomography is coincident with the one suggested for the active seismic line. Each electrode should be therefore located close to each geophone of the seismic line, in order to have a good overlap of the final seismic and resistivity sections.

As a consequence, the equipment used for the acquisition should include:

- digital resistivity meter (minimum 48 channels) capable of measuring and storing electrode contact resistance values and performing repeated measurements and standard deviation calculation for the quadrupoles identified in the preloaded measurement sequence;
- steel electrodes (minimum 48) and related connections to multi-channel cables.

The ERT should be acquired with an electrode configuration appropriate for the purposes of the work (Wenner-Schlumberger, or dipole-dipole). The dipole-dipole configuration is more sensitive to lateral changes in resistivity, while the Wenner-Schlumberger configuration demonstrates greater sensitivity to vertical variations in resistivity and is also characterized by greater depth of investigation for the same length of surface spreading. For this reason, at least measurements with this quadrupole configuration are suggested.

Suggested acquisition parameters include:

- Current injection time for each measurement (current electrodes) ≥ 250 ms;
- Voltage to be achieved for each measurement (potential electrodes) min 250 mV;
- Number of measurement repetitions per single quadrupole: 3 to 5;
- Standard deviation of single quadrupole measurements: <3%.

D) Processing methods

Active seismics

The processing of active seismic data involves the following analyses:

- **Refraction Seismic tomography**
The goal of refraction analysis is the retrieval of P-wave velocity (VP) model under the investigated line. First arrival time picking is performed on the traces related to the different shot gathers acquired along the line. The first arrival times are then input for an inversion algorithm allowing to retrieve the VP velocity section.
- **Surface wave tomography**
The acquired traces are windowed and used to estimate local dispersion curves (DCs) of surface wave propagation (Rayleigh wave velocity as a function of frequency). The retrieved DCs are input of an inversion algorithm allowing to retrieve a shear-wave (VS) velocity section.
- **Estimation of the mechanical parameters**
Once the VP and VS sections have been estimated, the Poisson's ratio (ν), dynamic Shear Modulus (G) and Young's Modulus (E) of the embankment materials can be estimated on a grid of nodes for which VP and VS estimations are available, following:

$$\nu = \frac{V_p^2 - 2V_s^2}{2(V_p^2 - V_s^2)} \quad (1)$$

$$G = \rho V_s^2 \quad (2)$$

$$E = 2G(1 + \nu) \quad (3)$$

where ρ refers to the density of the embankment materials that should be estimated through independent methods.

The quantification of ν , E and G provides fundamental inputs for the numerical modeling of the structural response of the embankments.

Passive seismics

The processing of passive seismic recordings is devoted to the identification of possible resonance frequencies of the embankments from the ambient seismic noise analysis. The horizontal-to-vertical spectral ratio (HVSr) method is applied. It consists in computing the ratio between the spectral content of the horizontal components (retrieved from N and E recordings) and the vertical one. The plot of HVSr as a function of frequency may highlight clear and sharp peaks at specific frequencies that are interpreted as resonance frequencies of the structure.

The numerical modeling of the vibration modes of the embankment can use these experimental results as a proxy for the validation of the simulations and as a further constraint to understand the structural response.

Electrical Resistivity Tomography

The field measurements are used as input to an inversion algorithm to retrieve a section of electrical resistivity tomography within the investigated embankment. The distribution of electrical resistivity can highlight differences in the grain size and compaction degree of the construction materials, as well as inhomogeneities in the water content. The interpretation of the resistivity section, combined with the results of the active seismic methods, is therefore suitable for the detection of weaknesses in the structure.

Integration of seismic refraction and surface waves tomography, jointly with electrical resistivity tomography can further provide qualitative and quantitative information on the mechanical properties of the materials and hydrogeological properties, with special reference to saturation and porosity. Optimization algorithms can be developed for petrophysically and geologically guided inversion of the different geophysical methods.